

Television Advertisements: Impact on Children

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Abstract:

Background of study: Advertising is a form of communication used to promote or sell something. Children spend many hours daily watching television. Increased exposure to television advertisement is associated with increased consumption of product advertised.

Objectives:To assess the impact of viewing television advertisement on the behaviour of children as perceived by parents.

Methods: An exploratory study was conducted on 100 parents of children in age group of (3-12 years) which were selected by convenience sampling technique.

Result: All children watch television and television advertisements; from which 60% spend <30 minute on television. About 73% of children give preference to food advertisements. Majority (83%) of parents reported that advertisements help in learning good habits and they also reported that 88% demand chocolate, candies and jellies after watching television advertisements. Three fourth i.e. 74% said that their children show temper-tantrum due to effect of advertisements

Keywords:- Television advertisements viewing, impact, behaviour, perceived.

I. INTRODUCTION

Advertising is a form of communication used to persuade an audience to take some action with respect to products, ideas or services (George G,2012). The advertising world is getting bigger every minute and every second of the day, people are finding creative write or design to showcase their products in very unique to make a lasting impression on the people (Murty TN et al.,2013).

Television is one of the strongest medium of advertisement, because due to its mass reach, it can influences individuals attitude, behavior, lifestyle, exposure and other aspects (Abiden ZUI and Salaria MR,2009). Most of the children spend about 3 to 4 hours daily watching television (Abiden ZUI and Salaria MR,2009). Children are emerging as a strong consumer segment which has a high influence on the parents buying decision with respect to item of own consumption and family (Murty TN et al.,2013).

Television advertisements directly affect children's eating habits and their food consumption (Arnas YA,2006). Children buying behavior also depends upon TV viewing hours because when children watch more TV they watch more advertisements and purchase more products (Hameed A,2014). Children like creativity and innovation, so the message of advertisement should be creative and innovative (Rathod MR, 2012).

Most of the advertisements related to food products are shown on child related programs like cartoon channels, it include advertisements related to healthy or unhealthy food products like candy, chocolate, chips, milk products, breakfast cereals, soft drinks and salty foods with no fruits or vegetables are shown. But children are easily attracted toward the unhealthy food products then they pressurize their parents to buy those food products. This study aims to investigate the impact of food advertisement on children's in India and their influence on parental requisites.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

An exploratory design was used to study television advertisements viewing and its impact on behaviour of children as perceived by parents. The target population for conducting research study consisted of all the parents of children in the age group of 3 to 12 years residing in a selected urban area. Convenience sampling technique was used to collect data.

The tool for data collection was a structured interview schedule & it had following sections:

Part A: Socio demographic data which include: age, gender, number of siblings, religion, class of child, education of mother and father, working status of mother and father, type of family and socio economic status of family.

Part B: Questionnaire to assess various television advertisements viewed by children.

Part C: Questionnaire to assess television advertisements viewing and its impact on behaviour of children in age group of 3-12 years as perceived by parents.

III. RESULT

From 100 children, 36% of children were in age group of 7-9 years. More than half i.e. 61% of children were males and 39% were females. Slightly less than half i.e. 42% of children had two siblings. Slightly less than half (42%) of children were in 1st -3rd class. More than two third (69%) of children belonged to Hindu religion. Majority (80%) of mothers of children were non-working. Almost 98% fathers of children were working. Two third i.e. 66% of children belonged to nuclear family. As per socio-economic status, more than half i.e. 52% of children belonged to Upper middle III class. As per educational status, slightly more than half i.e. 55% mothers and 53% of fathers were educated upto senior secondary level.

Out of 100 children all of them watch television. Three fourth (73%) of children give preference to food advertisements, 21% prefer toys advertisements and 5%

prefer clothes related advertisements, only 1% children prefer hygiene related advertisements. Out of 100, 73% children get distracted from their on-going activity during their favourite advertisements. Majority (87%) of them watch television advertisements with their own interest and only 13% watch due to sibling pressure. Majority of them i.e. 86% children watch cartoon character advertisements. More than two third(83%) of parents reported that advertisements help in learning good habits, three fourth

(78%) reported that advertisements increase knowledge regarding latest innovations and motivate the child about future prospects. More than half (64%) children demand health drink powders and 61% of children get knowledge about healthy food products from advertisements as reported by parents. Less than half (44%) children suffered with cough after eating food products which are advertised on television.

N=100

Impact on behavior pattern	f*(%)
Show temper tantrum	74
Insisted you to go to restaurants	61
Accidents after viewing advertisements while performing various stunts	36
Misinterpret the message	24

Table 1: Impact of television advertisements on behavior pattern of children as perceived by parents.

**Multiple response table*

Table 1: depicts that out of 100 children, three fourth i.e. 74% children show temper-tantrum due to effect of advertisements, 61% children insist their parents to go to restaurants after viewing food advertisements, 36% suffered

with accidents after viewing advertisements and one fourth i.e. 24% children misinterpret the message in advertisements as reported by parents.

N=100

Positive impact of advertisement	f*(%)
Learn good habits	83
Knowledge regarding latest innovations	78
Motivation about future prospects	78
Demand for health drink powders	64
Knowledge about healthy food products	61

Table 2: Rank order of positive impact of television advertisements on behavior pattern of children as perceived by parents.

**Multiple response table*

Table 2: depicts that majority (83%) of parents reported that advertisements help in learning good habits, three fourth (78%) reported that advertisements increase knowledge regarding latest innovations and motivate the child about future prospects. More than half (64%) children demand health drink powders and 61% of children get knowledge about healthy food products from advertisements as reported by parents.

more than 30 minute, on television advertisements. Study conducted by Chamberlain LJ et al (2006) concluded that time of advertisement viewing is significantly linked with requests for advertised toys and foods/drinks.

More than two-third (73%) of children get distracted from their on-going activity during their favourite advertisements and 87% children watch advertisements with their own interest and 13% children watch due to peer pressure.

IV. DISCUSSION

Out of 100 children all of them watch television and television advertisements.

In the present study, three by fourth (73%) of children give preference to food advertisements. In concordance to this study conducted by Olivares et.al(1999) in US on 786 children, concluded that one third of children prefer food advertisements followed by 21% prefer toys advertisements, 5% prefer clothes related advertisements and only 1% children prefer hygiene related advertisements. These results are in concordance with the study of Ofcom (2006) conducted on children of age group 2-11 years in daily life home settings, he depicted that advertisements works in influencing children's food preferences.

In the present study, 60% of children spend less than 30 minutes on television advertisements, 40% of them spend

There is increase in knowledge regarding latest innovations in 78% children, 78% are motivated about future prospects, 83% learn good habits and 61% get knowledge about healthy food products by television advertisements it is concordance to this study. Children Advertisements and their effects on family purchasing behavior: A Study of Cannanland, states that existing of new products in market increases and broadens knowledge of children. This study is in concordance to study conducted by Peterson et.al (1984) on 106 children in US concluded that exposure to T.V. advertisements increase knowledge related to products high in nutritional value. Nearly 81% children demands for soft drinks, 80% for junk foods, 64% for healthy drink powders, 88% for candies, chocolates and candies. 57% children demands for dress and costumes, 54% for stationary items. Nearly two-third, 61% children insist

parents to go to restaurants and 74% children shows temper tantrum.

In present study, Most of the children, (82%) children demands for items which are loaded with free gifts there results are in concordance with the study The Extend, nature and effect of food promotion to children given by Olivares et. al(1999)conducted study on 786 school going girls in Chile, he found that nearly three-quarters children purchase food products that offers free gifts and prizes. This effect is greater among children of average and low socio-economic group as compare to children of higher socio-economic status.This study is in concordance to study conducted by Atkin(1975) b et. al in US on 516 children.

Children suffers from many diseases after eating food items shown in television advertisements like 21% children suffers from loose stools and vomiting, 10% from cavities, foul smell, staining of teeth. It leads to change in eating pattern of 21% children, sore throat in 26%, cough in 44%, cold in 24% children, and allergies in 5% children.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

- There should be strict television watching hours for children.
- Parents should accompany their children while watching television to guide them.

VI. CONCLUSION

Maximum parents perceive that due to Television advertisement have negative impact on children the perceived negative impact include showing temper-tantrum, insisting their parents to go to restaurants after viewing food advertisements etc. Some parents reported that advertisements have some positive impact on children like learning good habits.

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